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Research Article

**ADVERSE RESPIRATORY HEALTH AND DECREASE IN
LUNG FUNCTIONS AMONG COAL INDUSTRIES WORKERS
IN SOUTH PUNJAB****Dr. Maryum Yousaf¹, Dr. Zareen Arshad², Dr. Atia Batool³**^{1,3}WMO in Civil Hospital Bahawalpur²Sir Syed College for Medical Sciences Trust (for Girls) Karachi**Article Received:** May 2020**Accepted:** June 2020**Published:** July 2020**Abstract:**

Objective: Employees extracted dust, gas gases, petroleum vapors etc. If safe work practices are insufficient, this may lead to negative respiratory health and deterioration of lung function in employees. The purpose of this study is to assess the condition of the respiratory system and lung function in employees of the coal industries.

Place and Duration: In the Pulmonology department of Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Methods: This study is a cross-sectional study conducted to monitor respiratory health and lung function among employees of the coal industries. A total of 87 tunnel employees were recruited for this study, which was exposed to dust excavated during work practices at the construction site. These workers were compared with 53 controls with the same socioeconomic status and were not professionally exposed to dust. Respiratory symptoms were reported using a questionnaire. Spirometry was performed for FEV1 (forced expiratory volume for 1 second) and FVC (mandatory vital capacity) tests of exposed and controlled subjects.

Results: Most of the symptoms reported by tunnel workers are shortness of breath (25.28%) and sputum causing cough (25.28%). Both parameters of lung function, viz. It was found that FEV1 and FVC were significantly reduced among tunnel workers ($p < 0.01$) compared to controls. There was a significant negative correlation between dust exposure time and FEV1 and FEV1 / FVC ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusion: As a result, we found poor respiratory health and reduced lung function, which are associated with tunnel workers exposure time.

Key words: respiratory system health, lung functions.

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INTRODUCTION:

Exposure to dust and chemical sprays among coal workers is a major factor affecting respiratory health and lung function. Coal workers suffer from respiratory diseases. During tunnel construction, a large amount of soil dust and sand is released during the excavation process. Previous studies have shown that tunnel workers are exposed to both dust and gas pollution. Previous studies have documented an increased risk of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and a reduction in long- and short-term lung function in tunnel workers. Tunnel and mine construction workers are exposed to dust during drilling and blasting operations. When drilling, contact with oil mist and oil mist may occur. During tunnel construction, more efficient drilling equipment can produce more oil vapor per unit of time. Occupational asthma and pulmonary fibrosis can be caused by exposure to oil vapors. Worsening of lung function due to exposure to nitrogen dioxide (NO) during tunnel construction has also been reported. Poor ventilation, microclimate and air pollution are the main environmental features that can lead to various respiratory disorders in underground tunnels. Dust from excavations, gas gases, oil vapors, etc. This is a cross-sectional study to assess respiratory health and lung function among exposed employees of the Coal industries.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Study design and population

This is a cross-sectional study conducted in the Pulmonology department of Bahawal Victoria Hospital Bahawalpur for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020 to examine respiratory and lung health. 87 employees participated in the study. They were exposed to dust excavated during work. These employees exposed to dust were compared with 53 controls at the same socioeconomic level and were not previously exposed to occupational dust. These employees voluntarily participated in this study and their written consent was obtained. The study was approved by the corporate ethics committee.

Questionnaire

The self-given questionnaire was used to learn about sociodemographic features, education and smoking habits. Other information on workplace practices and respiratory symptoms that they report was also obtained through this study. The use of personal protective equipment (PPE) in the workplace, the importance of PPE in professional practice, awareness of the negative impact of exposure to dust on respiratory health and exposure to dust (hours) per day are self-reported respiratory symptoms such as shortness of breath, dry cough: worker sputum, wheezing, chest pain, etc.

Professional knowledge

The workers did their job at the construction 10 hours a day, 6 days a week. During work, they are exposed to extracted dust due to various excavations. Dust is exposed to the mouth and nose, eventually passing to the upper and lower respiratory tract, causing drilling, sanding, charging, etc., causing some acute and chronic respiratory symptoms. Employees involved in activities. However, most employees wear masks at work, but due to their small size and constant pressure on the work environment, they are still exposed to dusty digging.

Spirometry

For respiratory function tests, spirometry was performed using FEV1 (forced expiratory volume for 1 second), PEFr (maximum expiratory flow rate) and FVC (forced lifetime) for each employee's lung failure (tunnel and control staff). spirometer (PIKO-1, Great Britain in accordance with the recommendations of the American Thoracic Society standards). The purpose of the lung function test is to assess lung failure in subjects. The volunteer performed the lung function test three times in a sitting position, allowing sufficient rest between repetitions. The best PEFr, FEV1 and FVC values were recorded from three tests for each patient. The results were interpreted on the basis of estimated values of lung function parameters calculated using the reference equation for the Indian population.

Statistics analysis

Descriptive statistics were generated for demographic parameters in the control group and tunnel employees. Frequencies and percentages are shown for all quality parameters. The Student's t-test was used to compare the mean values of continuous variables (demographic parameters and spirometry parameters) between the control group and the exposed group. A chi-square test is included to compare categorical results (respiratory symptoms). Linear regression analysis was performed taking into account daily dust exposure as an independent variable, and FEV1, PEFr and FEV1 / FVC as dependent variables, respectively. The significance criterion was defined as $p < 0.05$. All statistical analyzes were performed using IBM SPSS Statistics version 20.

RESULTS:

General information about tunnel employees

Table 1 shows the physical and professional characteristics of tunnel workers. The mean and range of variables viz. Age, height, weight, BMI are displayed. The average professional experience in the tunnel was 5.71 ± 7.31 years, from 1 to 37 years. The time of exposure to the powder (daytime hours) is 7.46 ± 3.48 , in the range of 1 to 15 hours.

Table 1 Physical and occupational characteristic of construction workers

Variables	Mean $\pm$ SD (N=87)	Observed range
Age (years)	31.34 $\pm$ 8.74	21-58
Height (cm)	167.81 $\pm$ 8.42	151-188
Weight (Kg)	73.74 $\pm$ 12.87	53-114
BMI (Kg/m ²)	26.14 $\pm$ 3.85	18.82-39.81
Occupational experience (years)	5.71 $\pm$ 7.31	1-37
Exposure period (hours per day)	7.46 $\pm$ 3.48	1-15

Table 2 shows the incidence of respiratory health symptoms among workers. Reported symptoms among tunnel workers include breathing difficulties during the test, sputum producing cough (thick sputum), coughing during awakening, wheezing during work. Most symptoms reported were dyspnea (25.28%) and cough-producing sputum (25.28%). Table 3 shows the results of lung function tests of tunnel workers. Parameters of lung function, viz. FEV1, FVC, FEV1 / FVC and employee controls were obtained by spirometry. All these parameters of pulmonary function were significantly reduced in employees compared to controls ($p < 0.01$).

Table 2 Frequency of respiratory health symptoms among construction workers

Respiratory health symptoms	No. of workers N (%) (N=87)
Shortness of breath	22 (25.28%)
Shortness of breath during the job	16 (18.39%)
Coughing that produces phlegm (thick sputum)	22 (25.28%)
Coughing during sleeping that wakes up	8 (9.19%)
Wheezing	11 (12.64%)
Wheezing during the job	7 (8.04%)

Table 3 Lung function tests of construction workers

Lung function parameters	Controls Mean $\pm$ SD (N=53)	Dust exposed workers Mean $\pm$ SD (N=87)	Significance
FEV1	2.47 $\pm$ 0.54	1.68 $\pm$ 0.80*	$p < 0.01$
FVC	2.52 $\pm$ 0.47	1.38 $\pm$ 0.87*	$p < 0.01$
FEV1/FVC	1.74 $\pm$ 0.21	1.21 $\pm$ 0.89*	$p < 0.01$

Correlation of lung function tests with dust exposure.

Table 4 shows the correlation of lung function tests with daily dust exposure (hours per day) among tunnel workers. There was a significant negative correlation between the exposure time to dust and FEV1 and FEV1 / FVC. However, no significant association was found between FVC and exposure time.

Table 4 Correlation of lung function tests with daily dust exposure among construction workers

Correlation of lung function parameters with daily dust exposure (hours per day)	R-value	Significance
FVC	0.18	$p = 0.16$ (not significant)
FEV1	-0.28	$p < 0.05$
FEV1/FVC	-0.45	$p < 0.001$

DISCUSSION

In this study, we found a significant reduction in respiratory health symptoms and lung function parameters in tunnel workers. These respiratory symptoms and deterioration of lung function, extracted dust, gas fumes, oil vapors etc. In the workplace. Previous studies have shown that FEV1 and PEFR are significantly lower in tunnel workers compared to controls. Galea et al. It was found that in 2015, reduced lung function was attributed to

exposure to many harmful substances such as respirable dust, respirable crystalline silica and exhaust emissions from diesel engines operating in tunnels at workplaces. We found a reduction in lung function in this study. Exposure between FEV1 and FEV1 / FVC between tunnel employees was significantly correlated with exposure time (daytime hours). Our findings indicate compliance with previous similar studies. Bakke et al. The study showed that in 2001 Tunnel workers changed their

short-term lung function and found a significant reduction in forced vital capacity (FVC) and forced expiratory volume in one second. (FEV1) compared to the reference group for several days' exposure of workers. In another study, a significant reduction in lung function parameters was observed in tunnel workers after 1 year of exposure to dust and gas. Ulvestad et al. It was found that exposure to long-term accumulated dust caused a significant reduction in lung function in tunnel workers over 8 years of observation. Regarding respiratory symptoms, the study found that tunnel workers had significantly higher respiratory symptoms, especially shortness of breath and productive cough. A previous study showed similar results reported by tunnel workers during the day compared to reference groups for more frequent coughing, difficulty breathing during exercise, and chest tightness and wheezing. Longitudinal studies have shown that exposure to respirable dust is the most important risk factor for respiratory symptoms. In our study, some tunnel workers were illiterate and most tunnel workers had a lower education. Breathing with mining dust, gases, oil vapors, etc. Awareness of their toxic effects and exposure can help them follow safe work practices to minimize exposure and thus reduce related respiratory diseases.

CONCLUSION:

As a result, this study showed a significant reduction in lung function parameters among tunnel workers. A significant correlation was found between dust exposure time and lung function parameters. Breathing difficulties and a productive cough were the most commonly reported symptoms by employees. The exposure assessment for hazardous substances was indirectly used as an estimate of exposure during working time, but not by sampling at the workplace, which is a limitation of this study. Future research is proposed to measure respirable dust in the workplace using personal monitors as well as permanent monitoring stations and to investigate their relationship to lung function parameters and respiratory symptoms.

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